

The Level Of Anxiety Among Students Of Racket Games In The Faculty Of Physical Education And Sports Sciences At The Hashemite University

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University. The researcher's used the descriptive approach - survey method to apply this study. The study sample includes (120) male and female students from the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University, (65) males and (55) females. The researcher's used the Spielberger Anxiety Scale to gather information for the study. The results showed that the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University was of a high level, ($M=3.94$). The results also showed that there were statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) due to gender variable, in favor of male students. The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences due to the variable (type of game).

Introduction

Sports psychology is a basic specialty in the field of sports training in general as it deals specially with the dimensions of behavior resulting from practicing different sports, so the preparation of high level players shouldn't include lots of operations that are considered basic sides in training. Psychological preparation, along with skill and tactical preparation, has become an integral part of the process of teaching, educating and training athletes and preparing them to compete in sports competitions.

Racket games are among the most important games that have contributed to achieving good results for some countries regionally and internationally, represented in badminton, table tennis and squash.

(Al-Amayreh et al., 2003) indicate that sports psychology aims to achieve a set of interrelated goals, as it seeks to understand and explain sports behavior and know the reasons for its occurrence and the factors affecting it. Psychology also seeks to predict what sports behavior will be based on relationships existing among the various sports phenomena, which are related to psychological aspects, and thus control sports behavior by modifying it, directing and improving it to what is desired, such as building social relationships, influencing others, controlling anger, staying away from anxiety, being rebellious and elevating mental health by identifying and treating mental illnesses or preventing them. .

Ikhlas Abdul Hafeeth (2002) believes that those interested in studying sports behavior have strived to use psychology in increasing the level of motivation towards achieving the best achievement by taking into account the needs and desires of athletes to achieve the greatest achievements; therefore it turns out that those interested in sports behavior are still studying important topics in sports psychology such as personality, motivation, psychological stress, burnout, sports violence, sports aggression, sports frustration, and understanding the thoughts and feelings of athletes.

She adds that athletes are exposed to various situations and circumstances during training and competitions, which may expose them to certain psychological pressures that depend on the type of competition results or sports achievements. When these pressures occur, the body begins to defend these pressures that help in facing these pressures and that may affect the health of athletes. The repeated exposure to severe psychological stress may lead to negative effects on sports performance, a defect in athletes' mental health. The ability of players to confront the causes of stress depends on the player's personal characteristics, such as the player's awareness of the stressful situation, and his response to psychological pressure. Each player has a personality that distinguishes him. Personality is described as a set of individual characteristics, inclinations, and fixed individual differences in behavior. Various sports have a significant role in directing some psychological characteristics of players. Personality characteristics of group games differ from those of individual games. In group games, those characteristics differ from one game to another, for example, the psychological characteristics of football players may differ from those of basketball players, and these characteristics may also

differ in racket games. The psychological characteristics of badminton players may differ from the psychological characteristics of table tennis players.

(Khatab, 2009) considered sports psychology is one of the important elements that have a direct impact on developing and improving the level of performance of athletes, and it is an important topic of studies in the field of physical education. Its importance appears by linking it with other sports sciences so as to study the motives driving sports behavior, which affect the cognitive, human and athletic aspect. Psychologists have begun to focus their energies on mental, intellectual and psychological abilities in all sports. Their attention focused on the diverse and changing mental abilities and how they contribute to the high and low performance of athletes and at the same time they focused their interests on why psychological stress that occur to athletes, which may lead to a group of important errors during performance.

(Cox, 2007) believes that there are many negative psychological characteristics that constitute a main obstacle to achieving high sporting achievement, especially in sports competitions, including violence, aggression, anxiety, and psychological burnout, as it is the point of falling for players in various sports.

(Luiselli, et al., 2011) states that the interest of many researchers and experts has focused on selected aspects of psychology such as (emotional, mental, and sensory motivational dimensions) in the field of sports depending on the physical activity practiced, whether competitive or recreational. Researchers are interested in finding a two-dimension. On the one hand, they are interested in analyzing how sports actions are monitored and controlled by various psychological processes, and on the other hand, they seek to understand sports actions and their relationship to psychological processes such as mental and emotional processes, which aim to enhance the logical understanding of logical behavior on both the theoretical and applied levels.

The concept of anxiety has gained great popularity among psychiatrists and psychologists as a cause and a manifestation of neurosis. Ali Al-Beek et al. (2000) indicated that what we have known about anxiety disorders and the consequent psychological diseases during the current years is more than what we have known about it during the past hundred years. .

Therefore, the researcher defined the concept of anxiety by searching for the concept of anxiety and the theories that explain it. Opinions and definitions about the concept of anxiety differed. Muhammad Allawi (2002) defined general anxiety as "a state of emotional tension that indicates the presence of internal danger or external danger that threatens the self and its essence is waiting, expectation, and inability to escape".

Mustafa Abu Rannan (2011) defines anxiety as "A change and disorder that occurs to the individual by the action of an internal or external stimulus, which pervades the soul and body together, which has a profound effect on the level of performance (25: 178).

The issue of anxiety, which is one of the psychological manifestations, occupies an important position in general psychology, in general, and in sports psychology in particular because of its clear and direct effects on the imbalance of psychological functions or physical functions or both. In the sports field, the player faces many situations that are directly and closely related, whether during sports training or sports competitions, and the situations, events and stimuli associated with each of them, and may have clear and direct effects on the athlete's behavior, level of abilities and skills; as well as his relationships with others (Allawi, 1998). Many researchers have pointed out that anxiety is considered as a warning or signal to mobilize all the individual's psychological and physical forces to try to defend and preserve one, and anxiety, if its intensity increases, may lead to a loss of psychological balance (which provokes the individual to try to restore control of this balance. Andler (referred to in Haddad, 2005) pointed out that there are five multiple dimensions that characterize the trait of anxiety, which are self-threat, physical danger, unconsciousness, and the threat of social evaluation, he also pointed out that there are two components of anxiety: cognitive, emotional arousal, or physical anxiety,

Ratib (1995) indicates that anxiety is one of the important emotions, which is one of the most important psychological phenomena that affect the performance of athletes, and that this influence may be positive that pushes athletes to exert more effort, or negatively hinders their performance.

Importance of the Study

The importance of the study lies in identifying the levels of anxiety among students of the Faculty of Physical Education in racket courses, as it is one of the teaching courses for students of the Faculty of Physical Education at the Hashemite University. And because these students are the bases on which they will build what they will learn during the university stage and what they will do after their graduation through their involvement in the teaching process or in the field of sports training.

Problem of the Study:

Upgrading any game requires knowing success and failure factors surrounding the game, which can influence its development for better. In this study, the focus will be the games of on (badminton, table tennis and squash). Through the researcher's work in the field of teaching and training table tennis and badminton at the university, the researcher noticed the lack of progress and development in achieving advanced results at the Arab, regional and global levels in these games with the availability of human financial capabilities to support these games. Players also show apparent dissatisfaction. They are constantly complaining and their talk is tainted

by frustration and anxiety, which leads to psychological burnout. This prompted the researcher to investigate through this study some negative psychological variables among the players of the table tennis, badminton and squash teams. This study perhaps reveals the negative behaviors, and presenting its results to the concerned federations to address these aspects, and thus obtain distinct results from the players of these games. Hence, the problem of the study appeared clearly to identify the negative psychological aspects faced by the national teams of racket games in Jordan.

Objectives of the Study

- Detecting the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University.
- Discovering if there is a difference in the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University due to the variables of gender and type of game.

Questions of the Study

- What is the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University?
- Does the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University differ according to gender and the type of game?

Limitations of the Study:

- **Human aspect:** Students of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences who are registered for the courses of table tennis, badminton, and squash, of the 120 male and female students.
- **Spatial aspect:** Sports activity hall (racquet games) The Hashemite University.
- **Time aspect:** The study was carried out in the first semester of the academic year 2020/2021

Procedural Definitions:

Racquet Games: Courses offered by the Hashemite University for the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences, in which the "racquet" tool is used, which are badminton, table tennis, and squash games.

Anxiety: Mustafa Abu Rannan (2011) defines it as a change and disorder that occurs to the individual by the action of an internal or external stimulus, which pervades the soul and body together and greatly, affects the level of performance.

Method and Procedure

Methodology:

The researcher's used the descriptive approach - survey method to apply this study.

Population and Sample:

The sample of the study consisted of the students of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University who are registered for the racket games course, (N=120) male and female students in the first semester of the academic year (2020/2021), (65) males and (55) females .

Tools of the Study:

The researcher's used the anxiety scale developed by Spielberger and others in 1970 and prepared his Arabic version Allawi (1994).

Validity and Reliability

The validity of the scale was confirmed by presenting it to a group of experts, "Appendix No. 1" (content validity), as well as using discriminatory validity, which is applied on the study sample. The results of the sample members are arranged in an ascending order, two groups were taken so that each group represents 25%. The first group is called the low level group and the second one is the high level group. The two groups were compared using t-test. The results presented in Table (1) indicated that there were statistically significant differences between the two groups, which confirm the validity of the discriminatory scale.

Table(1) The validity of the anxiety tool

Groups	Mean	SD	(t) value	Sig.
Low-level	60	6.26	12.104	*0.000
High-level	82.46	2.37		

*Significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The researcher's also verified the reliability of the scale using the internal consistency (Cronbach's alfa), where the reliability coefficient was (0.89).

Procedures of the Study:

After verifying the validity and reliability of the scale, the researcher's distributed it to the study sample members of the students enrolled in the Racket Games Course after clarifying the nature of the study, its objectives, and emphasizing that the information will be used for scientific research purposes, and that it will be completely confidential.

Statistical processing:

The researcher's used the means, standard deviations, t-test, one-way variance (ANOVA)

The Results

First: The results related to the first question: **What is the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University?**

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations were calculated, according to the responses of the study sample, the results are presented in Table (2).

Table (1): Means, standard deviations, ranks and level of anxiety of the items of the questionnaire

Item	Rank	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of anxiety
I feel confident while doing the exam	1	4,51	0,78	high
As I take the exam, I feel confused.	5	4,31	1,00	high
My thinking about the score I will get in a particular subject hinders my performance in the exam.	12	3,78	1,26	high
I feel like I'm almost freezing when I take important exams.	18	3,61	1,17	high
During exams I find myself thinking about my inability to complete my studies.	8	4,10	1,19	high
The more I tried in the exam, the more confused I became.	10	3,99	1,37	high
My thinking about poor performance in the exam affects my concentration negatively.	14	3,31	1,36	high
I feel very jittery when I take an important exam.	13	3,77	1,36	high
Even if I am ready to take an exam, I feel very nervous about it.	15	3,69	1,44	high
I get an intense feeling of turmoil right before I turn in the answer sheet for the exam.	17	3,60	1,34	high
During exams I feel very nervous.	11	3,92	1,22	high
I hope exams don't bother me too much.	16	3,66	1,19	high
During important exams I get so nervous that I feel an upset stomach.	9	4,00	1,31	high
I look like I'm beating myself up taking important exams.	19	3,59	0,91	high
I feel very uncomfortable while taking an important exam.	6	4,19	0,80	high
I get very annoyed before taking an important exam.	2	4,50	0,94	high
During the exam I find myself thinking about the results of my failure.	3	4,37	1,12	high
I feel like my heart is beating very fast while taking important exams.	20	3,56	1,41	high
After finishing the exam I try to prevent my discomfort with this exam but I can't.	7	4,15	0,88	high
While doing exams I get so nervous that I forget the information I know so well.	4	4,36	1,01	high
Total		3,94	1,01	high

Table (2) above shows the averages and standard deviations for the responses of the sample, as well as the rank of each paragraph of the anxiety questionnaire. All paragraphs were at a high level. The total mean of all the items was (3.9) and a standard deviation of (1.01). The item saying "I feel confident during my performance in the exam" ranked first (M= 4.51, SD = 0.78), followed by the item "I was very annoyed before taking an important exam" (M= 4.50, SD= 0.94). The two items that came last were "I beat myself while taking important exams" (M= 3.59 , SD= 0.91) and "I feel that my heart beats very fast while performing important exams" (M= 3.56 , SD= 1.41).

Second: The results related to the second question: **Does the level of anxiety among students of racket games in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University differ with the difference in gender and the difference in the level of the game?**

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations of the responses of the sample of the students' enrolled in Racket Games Course in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the Hashemite University were calculated, and the t-test is used to determine the differences between the average responses of the study sample members about the level of anxiety according to variables (gender, and game). Table (3) presents the results.

Table (3) Means, standard deviations, and results of the ((T)) test for the level of anxiety according to the variable of gender and type of game.

variable	Gender	Number	Mean	SD	t- value	df	Sig.
Gender	Male	65	3.73	0.52	4.00	1	*0.000
	Female	55	3.94	0.54			
Badminton	Male	20	3.92	0.50	3.44	1	* 0.000
	Female	10	3.75	0.51			
volleyball	Male	20	3.83	0.54	-1.4	1	0.299
	Female	20	3.97	0.57			
Squash	Male	20	3.40	0.67	2.894	1	0.634
	Female	15	3.58	0.60			
Tennis	Male	5	3.51	0.61	0.477	1	0.657
	Female	10	3.48	0.67			

*Significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Table (3) shows the means, standard deviations, and the results of the t-test for the responses of the study sample about the level of anxiety according to the gender variable and the type of game, where the results indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) according to the variable Gender at the general level and in favor of males ($M= 3.73$, $SD 0.52$), as well as the presence of statistically significant differences in favor of males in the game of badminton ($M=3.92$, $SD=0.50$), but there are no statistically significant differences between males and females on the rest of the games. The table also indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) on the variable (type of game).

Discussion of the results:

Concerning the results of the first question, which refers to identifying "the level of anxiety among the study sample in general", it was found that the level of anxiety was high among the members of the study sample in general. This result is considered positive, in comparison with the time allotted for these sports, as well as for the multiplicity and diversity of the skills specific for each game, and the difficulty of these skills and their need for motor accuracy and neuromuscular coordination, as well as the nature of these courses and the high effort they need to complete their requirements despite their differences, multiplicity and difficulty Skills and their need for motor accuracy and neuromuscular compatibility, as well as for the nature of these courses and the high effort they need to complete its requirements despite their differences, multiplicity and external difficulty (Makanay, 2000) who indicates that the high level of each of the traits of psychological anxiety, cognitive anxiety, and physical anxiety among older players with less years of practice and low level for younger players with more years of practice).

Concerning the second question, which refers to "identifying the level of anxiety in both male and female sample, as well as the type of game", it is noted the superiority of males over females in the level of anxiety at the general level as well as in the game of badminton. This is due to the difficulty of males' skills in different sports, as well as to the multiplicity of activities assigned to them, in which they outperform females, most of them using different equipment, and to the nature of badminton, which requires special requirements. This does not agree with (Simrin, 1995), which indicates that there are statistically significant differences in the levels and sources of anxiety in favor of females.

As for the relationship of the level of anxiety and the type of game among the study sample in different sports in general, there was no significant relationship between the level of anxiety and the type of game among the study sample in badminton, table tennis, squash, and tennis. This is due to the nature of racket games that require a high level of physical fitness and the development of the physical fitness elements of these games, which contribute to the development of players' skills in general.

Conclusions:

- The level of anxiety was high among the racket players at the Hashemite University.

- The level of anxiety among males was higher than the level of anxiety among females in the game of badminton, as well as at the general level. As well as for anxiety.
- There are no differences in the level of anxiety among the study sample according to the type of game.

Recommendations:

- 1- The necessity for teachers to take into account the psychological aspects of students while teaching them the skills of racket games to increase their desire to learn and reduce anxiety.
- 2- The need for teachers to pay attention to psychological preparation and its importance in preparing students psychologically to perform the required skills with confidence.
- 3- The need to find a solution by finding special times so that students can practice the skills of different racket games, to provide enough time to divide the skills and thus learning the games better and to reduce the state of anxiety by taking a better time in coexisting with the skills.
- 4- The need for teachers to motivate students and encourage them to build in them the desire to learn away from the threat and fear of failing.

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